

MORPHOLOGY OF MINT PLANT. MEDICINAL PROPERTIES AND IMPORTANCE. METHODS OF REPRODUCTION.

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Abstract: Information is provided on the production of medicinal mint plants and seedlings. At the same time, information is provided on seed yield, seed collection, planting dates, and agrotechnical maintenance methods, as well as methods of propagating medicinal mint seedlings.

Keywords: Mint root, stem, leaf, watering, biohumus, growing mint in containers, mint vitamins.

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, people have been using plants to treat various diseases. Medicinal plants are diverse in the territory of Uzbekistan, which are widely used in the treatment of various diseases, and are important as raw materials for the food and pharmaceutical industry and as feed for livestock. Information about the treatment of diseases on the basis of medicinal plants, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Al Khorazmi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, in their works, specifically focused on their morphology, philology, geographical distribution, and medicinal properties. They left information about tinctures made from roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds of plants. As a result of such a rich heritage of ours, today samples of the plant world are finding their place in medical practice based on deep research and tests.

Treatment with the help of environmentally friendly products made on the basis of medicinal plants is convenient, cheap and has certain advantages. Medicinal plants are very common in Uzbekistan, and their wide production as medicinal raw materials is of great importance.

Peppermint, a perennial medicinal plant widespread in Uzbekistan, is also widely used in folk medicine.

MORPHOLOGY OF THE MINT PLANT

The Latin name of the mint plant is MENTHA. Mint is a medicinal and ethereal plant belonging to the family of perennial herbaceous plants. It is a plant with a root stem, which grows up to 25-100 cm in height. The plant blooms throughout the summer. The stem is smooth like other parts of the plant. It is found in almost all regions of the city. It is grown in Europe, USA, Ukraine, Belarus, North Caucasus, China, India, Brazil and other countries. 20-25 species are distributed in the warm climate regions of the Northern Hemisphere.

There are 4 types of mint in Uzbekistan

- water mint
- asiatic mint
- bitter mint
- curly mint

like mints grow wild.

Mint

The stem of the mint is erect, 25 cm to 1 meter tall, the leaves are opposite, lanceolate or egg-shaped, with sharp toothed edges. The flowers of the mint plant are purple in color, gathered in an umbrella-like inflorescence, and bloom in May and October. Mint plant is a plant that loves light and moisture. It can be found wild on the banks of ditches and water.

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES AND USES OF MINT

The mint plant grows wild in the territory of Uzbekistan. Peppermint plant is used among our people in the fields of food, pharmaceuticals, medicine.

The mint plant contains a lot of vitamins, flavonoids, essential oils, and stimulants. Peppermint leaves contain 2.5-3% menthol, flowers 4-6%, stems 0.3%. Menthol affects the circulatory system and is used in pharmaceuticals.

Mint contains: Vitamins: C, B1, A, B5, B9, PP, B2, B6, phosphorus, manganese, iron, copper, magnesium, zinc, sodium, potassium, amino acids; betaine, arginine, fatty acid, organic acids, chlorogen, caffeine, valeric, vinegar, ascorbin, essential oils, menthofuran, rutin, resin, etc.

77% of peppermint plant consists of water and 2.5% of essential oils. The pleasant smell of peppermint is the result of essential oils and menthol.

100 g of mint leaves contain 1 g of fat, 7 g of carbon, and 4 g of proteins.

In medicine, tinctures prepared from the leaves of the mint plant are used to prevent nausea, as an expectorant, for a healthy heart, to drive away colds, to reduce pain, to increase the amount of water in the body, to satisfy thirst, to reduce It is used as a remedy for improving digestive functions, calming the nerves, treating colds and skin problems.

The stems and leaves of the mint plant are used in the production of medicinal products. The mint plant is planted because it has a pleasant smell. In early spring, it is used not only to make mint syrup, but also to make a pleasant juice from its leaves, to stop the activity of bacteria in the oral cavity, and in skin care.

No matter how useful the mint plant is, there are contraindications to its use:

Peppermint infusions reduce the production of male hormones in men, and are not recommended for people with low blood pressure, kidney and liver inflammation, and people with varicose veins.

The useful aspects of the medicinal mint plant are shown in the picture.

MINT PLANT PROPAGATION METHODS

The mint plant is mainly propagated vegetatively through rhizomes. In our conditions, it does not reproduce from its seeds because its seeds are destroyed. Peppermint is easy to grow in any country and can be used in salads, cocktails, teas and homemade aromatherapy oils.

Conditions for growing mint: Water - the more you water it, the more it will grow. Make sure there are holes in the bottom of the container. Fertilizer - You will need to fertilize the soil from time to time to keep it growing.

Growing Cuttings – Each time you cut mint to use, grow cuttings to start new plants. To do this, put the stem with two small leaves on top in water. Change the water daily so it will take root within a week, don't let the growing stems grow bend or cut any long stems and put them under the soil. They will soon turn into roots and

start growing more mint. Prune regularly - Prune mint as it grows, as this will encourage growth. Deep pot - The deeper the pot, the bigger the leaves. Fertilize weekly, water as often as possible. The more water and fertilizer is given, the more it will multiply. The more light the mint gets, the more it grows.

The process of growing mint in room conditions

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that it is important to meet the needs of medicinal plants distributed in our country and to supply medicinal plants to pharmaceuticals. For this, we need to study the medicinal plants found in Uzbekistan. We simply got acquainted with the composition of the mint plant and how many medicinal properties it has. There are many such medicinal plants, and it is up to us to study them and apply them to life.

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